

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART XIX. THIOINDIGOID DYES
DERIVED FROM FLUORENE-2:7-DISULPHONIC ACID

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The hitherto-unknown 2:1:7:8-fluoreno-*bis*-3'-hydroxy-1'-thiophene and its condensation products with *o*-diketones have been prepared with the object of studying the relation between colour and chemical constitution of thioindigoid dyes.

In Part XVIII of the series a study of the thioindigoid dyes derived from fluorene-2-sulphonic acid has been made (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 410). It was in view then to study similar thioindigoid dyes having two thioindigoid chromophores in the expectation that these dyes would be deeper in colour than the corresponding mono-thioindigoids. With this object, starting from fluorene-2:7-disulphonic acid (*Annalen*, 1912, 390, 210), an attempt has been made through the disulphochloride, dimercaptan and dithioglycollic acid, all unknown, to prepare the corresponding dithioindoxyl, 2:1:7:8-fluoreno-*bis*-3'-hydroxy-1'-thiophene, by the cyclisation of the latter. The attempt has been successful and as such the indoxyl, thus prepared, has been condensed with various *o*-diketones, and the desired dithioindigoid dyes have been obtained. Like other thioindoxyls, as already reported, this thioindoxyl also could not be obtained in a pure condition due to its susceptibility to oxidation. With alkaline potassium ferricyanide it produces a green solution, along with a green precipitate of the *bis*-indigo, but the yield of the latter is extremely poor.

As compared with the mono-thioindigoids, obtained from fluorene-2-sulphonic acid, these dyes are much deeper in colour, but in view of the sparing solubility and insolubility in certain cases of these dyes in alkaline hydrosulphite, a light shade has invariably been obtained. These dyes, as usual, show colour reaction with H₂SO₄ (conc.) and are also, like other similar such dyes, insoluble in alcohol, sparingly soluble in acetic acid, and highly soluble in nitrobenzene and pyridine.

The structures of these compounds may be represented as :

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Fluorene-2:7-disulphochloride.—Fluorene-2:7-potassium disulphonate (78 g.) was mixed with PCl_5 (80 g.) and POCl_3 (25 c.c.) and the mixture heated in an oil-bath at 140° for 2 hours when torrents of HCl fumes came out. The POCl_3 was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue treated with crushed ice and left overnight. The solid after powdering and thorough washing with water was dried. Yield of this crude product was 50 g. It was then crystallised from xylene, m.p. 225° , yield 36 g. (Found: C, 42.89; H, 2.35. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{S}_2$ requires C, 43.0; H, 2.2 per cent).

Fluorene-2:7-dimercaptan.—The above compound (4 g.) was reduced with tin and HCl (conc.) by heating for 30 hours. The residue after filtering and washing with HCl and water, was extracted with benzene three times; the extract was dried over CaCl_2 and the benzene distilled off. The yellowish residue, thus obtained, was crystallised from alcohol as long white needles, m.p. 165° , yield 1.4 g. (Found: C, 67.78; H, 4.41. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{S}_2$ requires C, 67.82; H, 4.34 per cent).

Fluorene-2:7-dithioglycolic Acid.—Fluorene-2:7-dithiol (17.2 g.) was treated with cold 10% NaOH (60 c.c.), filtered from a little insoluble matter, and the filtrate treated with monochloroacetic acid (14 g.), previously neutralised with caustic soda solution. Soon after the mixture had been heated on a water-bath, the whole solution solidified to a white cake. The heating was continued for an hour more to ensure complete reaction. Sufficient water was then poured inside and heated, whereby a complete solution was obtained. The hot solution after filtration was acidified with HCl till acid to Congo red when the thioglycolic acid separated out as a voluminous white precipitate. After cooling, it was filtered and washed. Yield of this crude product was 26.5 g. It was crystallised from alcohol as white needles, m.p. 216° . (Found: C, 59.1; H, 4.21. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$ requires C, 58.96; H, 4.04 per cent).

2:1-7:8-Fluoreno-bis-3'-hydroxy-1'-thiophene (I).—Finely powdered fluorene-2:7-dithioglycolic acid (10 g.) was suspended in petroleum ether (b.p. $60^\circ\text{--}80^\circ$; 100 c.c.) and to this PCl_5 (15 g.) was added. The mixture was then heated for an hour on a water-bath when fumes of HCl were given off and gradually a solution along with a little sticky matter was obtained. The clear solution after filtration was cooled in a refrigerator when crystals of acid chloride, m.p. 103° , separated. These crystals were then redissolved in fresh petroleum ether (100 c.c.) by warming and treated with anhydrous AlCl_3 (10 g.), and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for about 15 hours. The petroleum ether was then poured out and the residue

decomposed by crushed ice and HCl (conc.). The crude yellowish sticky mass, thus obtained, was dissolved in acetic acid and the clear acetic acid solution was used for condensation with various *o*-diketones, as described below. In caustic soda solution it dissolves with a greenish colour and is separated by HCl as a white precipitate, soon becoming reddish due to oxidation. Its alkaline solution with potassium ferricyanide forms a green precipitate of the *bis*-indigo.

2:1-7:8-Fluoreno-bis-thiophene-3:3-indol-indigo (IIa).—This compound was prepared by mixing together clear acetic acid solutions of isatin and fluoreno-*bis*-3'-hydroxy-1'-thiophene and heating the mixture with HCl (conc., 1 c.c.), when immediately a violet precipitate separated out. The heating was continued for 15 minutes more to ensure complete reaction, and filtered hot. The residue was washed first with acetic acid and then with alcohol. It was recrystallised from a large volume of acetic acid as a violet crystalline mass, m.p. above 300°. It dissolves in pyridine and nitrobenzene with a deep violet colour and dyes cotton from yellow hydrosulphite vat in deep violet shade. It dissolves in H₂SO₄ (conc.) with a violet colour. (Found: C, 69.57; H, 3.01. C₃₃H₁₈O₄N₂S₂ requires C, 69.71; H, 2.81 per cent).

The other dyes were also prepared in the same way from acetic acid solution in presence of a small quantity of HCl but these were crystallised from nitrobenzene, all melting above 300°. The properties of these dyes are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Structure No.	<i>o</i> -Diketone.	Colour of substance.	Dyeing shade.	Colour with conc. H ₂ SO ₄ .	Mol. formula.	Analysis.	
						Found.	Calc.
IIb	5:7-Dinitroisatin	Dark chocolate	Chocolate	Bottle-green	C ₃₃ H ₁₂ O ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂	N: 11.32	11.23
IIc	Acenaphthenequinone	Violet	Violet	Green	C ₄₁ H ₁₈ O ₄ S ₂	C: 76.87 H: 3.01	77.11 2.82
II d	3-Bromoacenaphthenequinone	Do	Light violet	Do	C ₄₁ H ₁₆ O ₄ Br ₂ S ₂	C: 61.73 H: 2.29	62.81 2.01
IIe	3-Nitroacenaphthenequinone	Dark colour	Could not be dyed	Chocolate	C ₄₁ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	C: 67.44 N: 2.31	67.58 2.19
II f	Phenanthrenequinone	Do	Do	Do	C ₄₁ H ₂₀ O ₄ S ₂	C: 78.18 H: 3.32	78.26 3.19
II g	Aceanthraquinone	Chocolate	Brown	Brown	C ₄₉ H ₂₀ O ₄ S ₂	C: 79.58 H: 3.17	79.67 2.98
III	Glyoxal sodium bisulphite	Violet	Greenish blue	Violet	(C ₁₉ H ₈ O ₄ S ₂) ₁₁	C: 68.54 H: 2.67	68.62 2.41

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